

1 Article

2 Model-Based Adaptive Joint Estimation of State of 3 Charge and Capacity for Lithium-Ion Batteries in 4 Entire Lifespan

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14 **Abstract:** In this paper, a co-estimation scheme of state of charge (SOC) and available capacity is
15 proposed for lithium-ion batteries based on the adaptive model-based algorithm. A three-
16 dimensional response surface (TDRS) in terms of the open circuit voltage, SOC and available
17 capacity in the scope of whole lifespan is constructed to describe the capacity attenuation, and the
18 battery available capacity is identified by genetic algorithm (GA) together with the parameters
19 related to SOC. The square root cubature Kalman filter (SRCKF) is employed to estimate the SOC
20 with the consideration of capacity degradation. The experimental results demonstrate the
21 effectiveness and feasibility of the co-estimation scheme.

22 **Keywords:** state of charge, available capacity, adaptive model-based algorithm, square root
23 cubature Kalman filter, joint estimation.
24

25 1. Introduction

26 Nowadays, energy crisis and environment damage have become main concerns of society and
27 require to be tackled with high attention [1]. Transportation electrification provides a possible
28 manner to reduce emissions and dependence on fossil. Electric vehicles (EVs) and hybrid EVs (HEVs)
29 are promising solutions which, however, require electrical energy storage systems to completely or
30 partially replace propelling power supplied by traditional internal combustion engines [2]. In this
31 context, applications of lithium-ion batteries have been intensively spurred due to their numerous
32 advantages such as wide environmental temperature operation capability, high energy density, long
33 lifespan, and large charge/ discharge current [3]. For lithium-ion batteries, state of charge (SOC) and
34 available capacity, usually provided by battery management systems (BMSs), are crucial parameters
35 for evaluation of electrical performance of battery as well as control of the vehicle.

36 Typically, estimation methods of SOC can be divided into four categories, including the coulomb
37 counting method, characterization parameter-based methods such as open circuit voltage (OCV)
38 method, model-based methods and data-driven methods. Amongst them, the coulomb counting
39 method [4] and OCV method [5] have been widely applied in BMSs of EVs because of their simplicity
40 and ease of implementation, whereas the former is prone to production large accumulated error due
41 to interferences or uncertainties of current sensors/ transducers and inaccurate initial value, and the
42 latter is not suitable for online estimation, as it usually costs long shelving time to acquire the OCV
43 value. With the development of computation technologies and machine learning, a variety of artificial
44 intelligence-based data-driven methods, such as neural networks [6] and support vector machine [7]

45 are proposed for SOC estimation by establishing black-box models. Data-driven methods feature
46 strong nonlinear mapping capability with high accuracy; however, these approaches show high
47 complexity and require a considerable amount of training data. Alternatively, model-based methods
48 have been widely investigated and applied for SOC estimation thanks to capabilities of online
49 application, high precision and independence of initial values. Conventional modeling manners
50 mainly includes electrochemical models and the equivalent circuit models (ECMs). Compared with
51 complicated electrochemical models, ECM is commonly used to describe electrical behavior of
52 batteries and subsequently estimate SOC due to its simplification and preferable precision. In [8], a
53 multi-model probability fusion algorithm is proposed to describe battery's electrical characteristics
54 and subsequently estimate the SOC. In model-based methods, combination of the battery model and
55 intelligent filtering algorithm is a hotspot in SOC estimation research. The frequently used filtering
56 algorithms include Kalman filtering (KF) [9], H-infinity filter (HIF) [10], particle filter (PF) [11] and
57 their various extensions. In particular, the extended KF (EKF) is widely employed to execute SOC
58 estimation using a first-order Taylor expansion on the basis of battery's nonlinear model [12].
59 Nonetheless, the second and higher order expansion is usually neglected, thus leading to slow
60 convergence rate and even divergence. The unscented KF (UKF) is exploited to estimate battery SOC
61 based on the recursive unscented transformation to approximate the nonlinear observation without
62 Taylor polynomial expansions [13]. The UKF shows better estimation precision and robustness than
63 EKF in strong nonlinear systems [14]. On the basis of radial-spherical cubature criterion, the cubature
64 Kalman filter (CKF) leverages a set of volume points to approximate the mean and covariance of
65 states with additional Gaussian noise [15]. Although CKF outperforms EKF and UKF in terms of
66 filtering divergence and estimation error, it is susceptible to inaccurate initial difference and
67 disturbances, and is difficult to guarantee symmetric and nonnegative definition of the covariance
68 matrix all the time. HIF is applied in state estimation and model parameters identification of batteries
69 due to its good anti-interference performance in high nonlinear systems [16]. PF exhibits attracting
70 advantages in solving nonlinearly non-Gaussian distribution problem and highlights more
71 application potential than EKF. Thus, it has been widely developed and applied in multifarious fields
72 such as batteries, robotics and navigation systems [17]; however, it is limited by strong dependence
73 on noise and time-varying parameters of system.

74 In addition, battery aging is an irreversible process with operation, the most intuitive appearance
75 is decline of capacity and increase of internal impedance [18]. In general, the attenuation process is
76 nonlinear, complex and even difficult to predict. To attain it, a body of algorithms have been
77 successfully proposed and applied to achieve capacity estimation, mainly including experimental
78 analysis methods and model-based methods. The most direct and easiest manner of evaluating the
79 capacity is to conduct the calibration test [19]. However, it is obviously time-consuming and only
80 supports offline estimation. Additionally, battery's impedance variation also highlights the capacity
81 degradation trend [20]. However, online electrochemical impedance measurement is not suitable for
82 practical applications due to its exceptional complexity of experiment. Motivated by these difficulties
83 and constraints, incremental capacity analysis (ICA) is introduced to conduct capacity estimation by
84 evaluating the increment of capacity in a certain charging interval [21]. Similar algorithms also
85 include differential voltage analysis (DVA) with the help of analyzing variation characteristics of
86 voltage curves in predetermined charge/discharge operations [22]. Yes, they can reflect aging
87 mechanism of batteries and highlight preferable accuracy; nonetheless, they are intractable to apply
88 in practice as chances of encountering the interval with predetermined current are seldom. Since it is
89 time-consuming to measure and determine the battery capacity directly; model-based estimation
90 approaches may supply an indirect manner to evaluate it. The model-based methods can leverage
91 adaptive algorithms (such as joint estimation approaches [24] and fuzzy logic algorithms [25]) to
92 identify the battery capacity. These algorithms are easy to be implemented and meanwhile
93 demonstrate preferable accuracy; whereas, in the model-based approaches, the battery capacity is
94 regarded as a key parameter or state variable and is obtained by parameter identification or estimated
95 together with SOC with an established circuit model or electrochemical model. From this point of
96 view, the model accuracy can directly affect the estimation accuracy of battery capacity.

97 The above-mentioned state estimation methods are mostly developed for either SOC or capacity
 98 estimation individually, rather than for both simultaneously. SOC refers to the residual capacity rate
 99 over nominal values, while SOH represents the nominal capacity value with operations. To certain
 100 extent, battery capacity shows the same significance as SOC, and essentially, they are tightly coupled
 101 with each other [25]. Apparently, SOC estimation based on the known and unchanged capacity
 102 exhibits certain limitations in practice. A common knowledge is that internal parameters of batteries
 103 change with degradation. The internal resistance will increase, and the capacity will decrease
 104 gradually, thus resulting in challenges and difficulties of estimating the SOC reliably and robustly.
 105 Consequently, it is critical to update the model parameters, particularly the capacity, in a timely
 106 manner. Motivated by this, a joint estimation scheme is proposed in this study to improve the
 107 estimation accuracy of SOC and capacity in the entire lifespan of battery. Firstly, a second-order
 108 resistance-capacitance (RC) based ECM is established, and the co-estimation scheme of SOC and
 109 battery capacity is presented. In it, the square root cubature Kalman filter (SRCKF) algorithm is
 110 employed to estimate the SOC; and meanwhile the battery capacity, as one of the key model
 111 parameters, is identified by the genetic algorithm (GA) based on the constructed three-dimensional
 112 response surface (TDRS). Finally, the estimation results of SOC and battery capacity are verified by
 113 different experimental validations over the entire lifespan. This study dedicates to the following two
 114 contributions: 1) A novel capacity estimation method based on a TDRS is proposed and the model
 115 parameters are updated synchronously; and 2) based on the capacity and parameters revision, a co-
 116 estimation scheme is established for the SOC and capacity estimation simultaneously against
 117 different degradation status.

118 In the remainder of this study, Section 2 details the second-order RC model and the experiment
 119 test profiles. In Section 3, the co-estimation scheme of capacity and SOC is elaborated. The validation
 120 results are exhibited and discussed in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 draws the main conclusions and
 121 future works.

122 2. The Lithium-ion Battery Model and The Experimental Details

123 2.1 Battery Modeling and Analysis

124 To better estimate battery states, various mathematical models have been established, including
 125 electrochemical models [26] and ECMs [27]. However, they differ greatly in accuracy, computation
 126 complexity and reliability. Considering precision and complexity of models, a second-order RC based
 127 ECM, as shown in Figure 1, is deployed in this work thanks to its relatively satisfactory precision and
 128 acceptable computation intensity [28]. As can be seen, it contains two parallel RC networks connected
 129 in series topology to characterize the battery polarization. Based on Figure 1, the circuit equation can
 130 be built, as:

$$131 \quad \dot{U}_s = -\frac{U_s}{R_s C_s} + \frac{I}{C_s} \quad (1)$$

$$132 \quad \dot{U}_l = -\frac{U_l}{R_l C_l} + \frac{I}{C_l} \quad (2)$$

$$133 \quad U_t = U_{ocv} - U_s - U_l - R_e I \quad (3)$$

134 where R_l and C_l indicate the internal resistance and capacitance of electrochemical polarization,
 135 and R_s and C_s denote the internal resistance and capacitance of concentration polarization. U_s
 136 and U_l denote the voltage drop across $R_s C_s$ and $R_l C_l$, respectively; U_t indicates the terminal
 137 voltage; I is the loading current; U_{ocv} stands for the open circuit voltage; and R_e represents the
 138 internal ohmic resistance. In addition, the SOC denotes the ratio of available remaining capacity over
 139 the rated capacity (the maximum available capacity), as:

$$140 \quad SOC(t) = SOC(t_0) - \frac{\int_{t_0}^t \eta_c I(t) dt}{Q_N} \quad (4)$$

141 where $SOC(t)$ indicates the SOC value at t , respectively, $SOC(t_0)$ stands for the SOC value at t_0 ,
 142 Q_N is the rated capacity of battery, and η_c represents the coulombic efficiency.

143

144

Figure 1. The second-order RC equivalent circuit model.

145 2.2 Experiments

146 The basic specifications of battery are illustrated in Table 1. The battery's nominal voltage is 3.6
 147 V and the nominal capacity is 2.55 Ampere hour (Ah). To characterize the battery's electrical
 148 performance, some prerequisite experiments are conducted, including accelerated aging test,
 149 performance test, and dynamic test. The accelerated cycle life aging test is carried out at 25 °C, which
 150 is divided into seven stages. They are separated by the cycles 0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150 and 180 (defined
 151 as cyc0, cyc30, cyc60, cyc90, cyc120, cyc150 and cyc180 hereinafter). The battery cell is charged by
 152 means of the constant current-constant voltage (CCCV) scheme with the current rate of 1C and
 153 discharged by means of constant current (CC) with the current rate of 2C in each cycle. Here, C
 154 denotes the rated capacity value of battery with the unit of Ah. The performance tests, including the
 155 capacity test and hybrid pulse power characterization (HPPC) test, are carried out periodically during
 156 the cycle life test. In addition, a typical dynamic test based on the urban dynamometer driving
 157 schedule (UDDS) is executed to verify the performance under dynamic operating conditions. Figure
 158 2 shows the decay variation of discharge capacity. It can be clearly observed that the discharge
 159 capacity basically remains unchanged from cyc0 to cyc30 and it tends to decline faster after 30 cycles,
 160 and the amount of electric energy decreases faster as the cycle number increases. After 180 cycles, the
 161 maximum discharge capacity decreases from the initial 2.614 Ah to 1.129 Ah, which remains only
 162 44.3% of the nominal capacity. The discharge capacity decreases to 1.97 Ah at the fifth stage (cyc120),
 163 which is 77.25% of the nominal capacity. When the capacity drops to 80% of the rated value, the
 164 battery should be abandoned; and therefore, only the experimental results of the first five aging
 165 stages are applied to analyze and verify the performance of proposed algorithm in this work.

166

Table 1. The specifications of the battery cell.

Material	Ternary lithium-ion battery
Nominal capacity	2.55 Ah
Nominal voltage	3.6 V
End-of-charge voltage	4.2 V
End-of-charge current	51 mA
End-of-discharge voltage	2.5 V

167

168 Furthermore, battery degradation not only features the capacity reduction but also embodies
 169 variation of the OCV-SOC relationship. The relationship curve between OCV and SOC at various
 170 aging status is presented in Figure 3. It is apparent that the OCV-SOC relationship curve changes
 171 gradually as the cycle number increases. When SOC is more than 20%, the trend of curves remains
 172 basically the same. However, when the SOC is less than 20%, especially under 10%, the OCV changes

173 significantly. Generally, to protect and extend the battery life of EVs, the battery discharge cut-off
 174 SOC is usually set to 10% or 20%. When the SOC ranges from 20% to 60%, the OCV at different aging
 175 status differs obviously, and the maximum difference value is 20 mV. When the SOC is more than
 176 60%, the OCV values at different aging status are relatively close, and the maximum difference is
 177 within 10 mV.

178

179

Figure 2. The decay of battery cell discharge capacity under 180 cycles.

180

181

Figure 3. The relationship curve of OCV and SOC at different aging stages.

182 3 The Joint Estimation of SOC and battery capacity

183 The framework of the joint capacity and SOC co-estimation is shown in Figure 4. It mainly
 184 includes four parts: the strategy module, the modeling module, the capacity and parameters
 185 estimation module as well as the SOC estimation module. First, the strategy module starts to
 186 accumulate the experimental data until the length of data is more than the preset threshold. Then,
 187 the capacity estimation module employs the GA to conduct the parameter identification and capacity
 188 estimation based on the acquired data and established model. After finding the model parameters
 189 and capacity, the SOC estimation module is triggered to estimate the SOC based on the SRCKF. Note
 190 that the modeling and parameters estimation modules are not invoked every time. The detail co-
 191 estimation procedure is elaborated in the following.

192 3.1 The Capacity Estimation Algorithm

193 The battery capacity is deemed to be a significant parameter that needs to be identified. Firstly,
 194 based on the OCV-SOC curves illustrated in Figure 3, a TDRS with respect to the capacity, SOC and
 195 OCV is constructed, as plotted in Figure 5. Next, the TDRS is imported into the established battery
 196 model. Finally, the usable battery capacity is incorporated into the battery model parameters and
 197 identified by the GA [29]. By this manner, the problem of usable battery capacity estimation can be
 198 transformed into the problem of searching the optimal OCV-SOC relationship match on the built
 199 TDRS by applying the optimization algorithm. It is worth noting that the ambient temperature plays
 200 an important influence on battery capacity. However, the temperature influence is not taken into
 201 account in this study, as the battery system onboard is generally equipped with a good thermal
 202 management system, thereby ensuring the temperature variation is within ± 5 °C [30].

203
204

Figure 4. The scheme of SOC and battery capacity co-estimation algorithm for lithium-ion batteries.

205
206

Figure 5. The three-dimensional response surface via capacity-SOC-OCV.

207 In consideration of accuracy and complexity, a fifth-order polynomial function is selected to
208 describe the relationship among OCV, SOC and capacity, as:

$$209 \quad U_{OCV}(SOC, C_{a,i}) = \alpha_{1,i} \times SOC^5 + \alpha_{2,i} \times SOC^4 + \alpha_{3,i} \times SOC^3 + \alpha_{4,i} \times SOC^2 + \alpha_{5,i} \times SOC + \alpha_{6,i} \quad (5)$$

210 where $C_{a,i}$ represents the available battery capacity at the i th capacity point. $\alpha_{j,i}$ ($j=1, \dots, 6$)
211 denotes the fitting coefficient of OCV and SOC at the i th capacity point, which is no longer a constant
212 and is herein defined as a quadratic function of $C_{a,i}$, as:

$$213 \quad \alpha_{j,i} = b_{2,i} C_{a,i}^2 + b_{1,i} C_{a,i} + b_{0,i} \quad (6)$$

214 where $b_{t,i}$ ($t=0,1,2$) denotes the capacity coefficient. The above equation can be rewritten into a
215 matrix form, as:

$$216 \quad [\alpha_{1,i}, \alpha_{2,i}, \alpha_{3,i}, \alpha_{4,i}, \alpha_{5,i}, \alpha_{6,i}]^T = \Gamma \times [C_{a,i}^2 \quad C_{a,i} \quad 1]^T \quad (7)$$

217 where Γ refers to a 6×3 capacity coefficient matrix, which can be obtained by the polynomial
218 fitting, and the results are described in (8).

$$\Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} 14.2473 & -57.3965 & 61.0568 \\ -39.1366 & 155.6827 & -165.5359 \\ 38.9053 & -151.7664 & 161.0539 \\ -16.8787 & 63.8408 & -66.9571 \\ 3.0020 & -10.7412 & 11.4284 \\ -0.1149 & 0.2951 & 3.2020 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Now, according to (5)-(8), a nonlinear relationship can be built among OCV, capacity and SOC. Once the SOC is determined, it will be a deterministic mapping function between OCV and SOC. Together with (1)-(3), the capacity identification can be conducted simultaneously with other parameters including those of the RC networks. During the parameters identification, the variation of model parameters is eventually reflected by the difference between the estimation result and terminal voltage. Based on the OCV model, the discrete mathematical expression of the second-order RC based ECM can be reformulated as:

$$U_{t,k} = U_{ocv,k}(SOC_k, C_a) - \exp(-\Delta t / \tau_s) U_{s,k} + R_s [1 - \exp(-\Delta t / \tau_s)] I_k - \exp(-\Delta t / \tau_l) U_{l,k} + R_l [1 - \exp(-\Delta t / \tau_l)] I_k - I_k R_e \quad (9)$$

where Δt indicates the time interval, and $\tau_s = R_s C_s$ and $\tau_l = R_l C_l$ belong to time constants. As can be seen from (9), the TDRS based on the OCV model in (5) is imported into the ECM. Hence, the difference of relationship between SOC and OCV at different capacity levels is eventually highlighted by the estimation results of the terminal voltage. In this manner, the battery capacity can be added into the model parameter series for identification. To attain it, the GA is employed to find the optimal combination of model parameters and capacity, in which the optimal parameter group to be identified can be expressed as:

$$\theta_{optimal} = [R_e, R_s, R_l, C_s, C_l, C_a] \quad (10)$$

During the identification process, the minimum root means square error (RMSE) of the terminal voltage is taken as the fitness function, as:

$$\begin{cases} \varphi(\theta_{optimal}) = \min |RMSE| \\ RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_k^N [U_{t,k} - \hat{U}_{t,k}(\theta_{optimal})]^2}{N}} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $U_{t,k}$ and $\hat{U}_{t,k}(\theta_{optimal})$ represent the measured terminal voltage and the estimated terminal voltage at step k , respectively. In addition, the constraints of optimization algorithm are subject to:

$$\begin{cases} 20\% \leq SOC \leq 100\% \\ 0.005\Omega \leq R_e, R_s, R_l \leq 0.1\Omega \\ 0.5s \leq \tau_s \leq 1000s \\ 0.5s \leq \tau_l \leq 1000s \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The setting of constraints is explained as follows. In practical applications, to avoid over-charge and over-discharge of the battery, the range of SOC is generally set to 20% to 100% for guaranteeing proper operation and extending service life of batteries [32]. The upper limits of internal ohmic resistance R_e , internal resistance R_l of electrochemical polarization and internal resistance R_s of concentration polarization are determined in terms of the specifications of batteries and the technical parameters supplied by the manufacturers. Their low limits are all determined to be 0.005 Ω based on the parameter calculation of ECM introduced in [33] as well as the experimental analysis. Meanwhile, the range of C_l and C_s can be deduced to be 100 F to 10⁴ F. τ_l and τ_s are time constants, $\tau_l = R_l C_l$ and $\tau_s = R_s C_s$. Hence, the range of τ_l and τ_s can be limited with 0.5 s to 1000 s. In summary, when the above-mentioned battery model parameters and capacity are identified, these parameters will be transmitted into the SOC estimation module. However, it is worth noting that the parameter identification based on the GA requires a certain amount of data to obtain an ideal identification result. Therefore, the capacity estimation method proposed in this paper only runs

255 when the data length reaches a pre-set condition and the determination of data length will be
256 discussed in the next section.

257 3.2 The SOC Estimation Algorithm

258 After obtaining the model parameters and battery capacity, the SRCKF is proposed to attain the
259 estimation of battery SOC with the cyclic recurrence based on the established second-order RC ECM.
260 In comparison with the traditional cubature Kalman filter (CKF), the SRCKF can directly perform
261 iterative update in the form of calculating square-roots of the covariance matrices during the filtering
262 process, which determines the non-negative definite value of covariance matrix and avoids the
263 divergence of filter [33]. In general, a discrete nonlinear dynamic system with enhanced noise can be
264 modeled, as:

$$265 \begin{cases} x_{k+1} = f(x_k, u_k) + w_k \\ z_k = h(x_k, u_k) + v_k \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

266 where $x_k \in R^n$ and z_k indicate the system state vector and the system output at time k ,
267 respectively. $f(\cdot)$ and $h(\cdot)$ denote the nonlinear system state function and nonlinear measurement
268 function, respectively. w_k stands for random process noise indicating uncertain input. v_k denotes
269 observation noise, which is generally employed to simulate sensor noise affecting output
270 measurement. Additionally, the corresponding covariance of w_k and v_k are Q_k and R_k ,
271 respectively. Based on the established ECM, the time-discrete state equation and measurement
272 equation can be respectively expressed, as:

$$273 \begin{bmatrix} U_{s,k+1} \\ U_{l,k+1} \\ SOC_{k+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \exp(-\Delta t / \tau_s) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \exp(-\Delta t / \tau_l) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_{s,k} \\ U_{l,k} \\ SOC_k \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} R_s & 1 - \exp(-\Delta t / \tau_s) \\ R_l & 1 - \exp(-\Delta t / \tau_l) \\ -\eta_c \Delta t / C_a \end{bmatrix} I_k + \begin{bmatrix} w_{1,k} \\ w_{2,k} \\ w_{3,k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$274 U_{l,k} = U_{ocv,k}(SOC_k, C_a) + [-1 \quad -1 \quad 0] \begin{bmatrix} U_{s,k} \\ U_{l,k} \\ SOC_k \end{bmatrix} + [-R_e] I_k + v_k \quad (15)$$

275 where the system state variable $x_k = [U_{s,k} \quad U_{l,k} \quad SOC_k]^T$, input variable $u_k = I_k$ and system output
276 $z_k = U_{l,k}$. In this study, The SRCKF algorithm is adopted to estimate the SOC, of which the general
277 process is summarized in Table 2, where n is the state dimension, and m denotes the total number of
278 volume points, which is twice of the state dimension. The sample $[1]$ indicates a complete set of fully
279 symmetric points, of which the set of points is obtained through the complete permutation of
280 elements of the n -dimensional unit vector $e = [1, 0 \dots 0]^T$ and the alteration of the element symbol.
281 $[1]_g$ represents that the point is centered at the g th point of $[1]$. \hat{x}_k and \hat{z}_k are the predicted state
282 and measurement, respectively. $S_{Q,k-1}$ and $S_{R,k}$ denote the square-roots of the process noise
283 covariance matrix Q_{k-1} and measurement noise covariance matrix R_k , respectively.

284 **Table 2.** The process of SOC estimation based on SRCKF algorithm

(a) Initialization:

$$\begin{cases} \hat{x}_{0|0} = E[x_0] \\ P_{0|0} = E[(x_0 - \hat{x}_{0|0})(x_0 - \hat{x}_{0|0})^T] \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Determine the initial value $S_{0|0}$ of square roots of error covariance matrix by the Cholesky decomposition:

$$S_{0|0} = [chol(P_{0|0})]^T \quad (17)$$

(b) Calculate the basic cubature points and weight:

$$\xi_g = \sqrt{\frac{m}{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \end{bmatrix}_g, (g = 1, 2, \dots, m) \quad (18)$$

(c) Iteration:

for $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$

Time update:

Step 1: calculate the cubature points:

$$X_{g,k-1|k-1} = S_{k-1|k-1} \xi_g + \hat{x}_{k-1|k-1} \quad (19)$$

Step 2: calculate the propagated cubature points:

$$X_{g,k|k-1}^* = f(X_{g,k-1|k-1}, u_k) \quad (20)$$

Step 3: calculate the predicted state:

$$\hat{x}_{k|k-1} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{g=1}^m X_{g,k|k-1}^* \quad (21)$$

Step 4: calculate the state weighted center matrix:

$$\chi_{k|k-1}^* = \frac{1}{\sqrt{m}} \begin{bmatrix} X_{1,k|k-1}^* - \hat{x}_{k|k-1} & \dots & X_{m,k|k-1}^* - \hat{x}_{k|k-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

Step 5: calculate the square-root of prediction error covariance matrix:

$$S_{k|k-1} = \text{Triu} \left[\chi_{k|k-1}^*, S_{Q,k-1} \right] \quad (23)$$

Measurement update:

Step 1: recalculate the cubature points:

$$X_{g,k|k-1} = S_{k|k-1} \xi_g + \hat{x}_{k|k-1} \quad (24)$$

Step 2: update the propagated measurement cubature points:

$$Z_{g,k|k-1} = h(X_{g,k|k-1}, u_k) \quad (25)$$

Step 3: estimate the predicted measurement:

$$\hat{z}_{k|k-1} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{g=1}^m Z_{g,k|k-1} \quad (26)$$

Step 4: evaluate the measurement weighted center matrix:

$$\zeta_{k|k-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{m}} \begin{bmatrix} Z_{1,k|k-1} - \hat{z}_{k|k-1} & \dots & Z_{m,k|k-1} - \hat{z}_{k|k-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

Step 5: estimate the square root of the innovation covariance matrix:

$$S_{zz,k|k-1} = \text{Triu} \left[\zeta_{k|k-1}, S_{R,k} \right] \quad (28)$$

Step 6: update the state weighted center matrix:

$$\chi_{k|k-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{m}} \begin{bmatrix} X_{1,k|k-1} - \hat{x}_{k|k-1} & \dots & X_{m,k|k-1} - \hat{x}_{k|k-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

Step 7: estimate the cross-covariance matrix:

$$P_{xz,k|k-1} = \chi_{k|k-1} \zeta_{k|k-1}^T \quad (30)$$

Moreover, update the Kalman gain, state and square root of the error covariance

Step 1: estimate the Kalman gain matrix:

$$W_k = \frac{P_{xz,k|k-1} / S_{zz,k|k-1}^T}{S_{zz,k|k-1}} \quad (31)$$

Step 2: estimate the final updated state:

$$\hat{x}_{k|k} = \hat{x}_{k|k-1} + W_k (z_k - \hat{z}_{k|k-1}) \quad (32)$$

Step 3: update the corresponding square-root of the error covariance matrix:

$$S_{k|k} = \text{Triu} \left[\chi_{k|k-1} - W_k \zeta_{k|k-1}, W_k S_{R,k} \right] \quad (33)$$

End

285 4. Verification and Discussion

286 4.1 Verification Study on Different Data Lengths

287 In this section, different data lengths are selected to investigate the effectiveness of the proposed
 288 co-estimation algorithm. Actually, the experimental data at different aging stages can be chosen to
 289 verify the SOC estimation of different data lengths. Nonetheless, as shown in Table 4, the estimation
 290 error of battery capacity is maximum at cyc30. Hence, to better verify the performance of proposed
 291 estimation algorithm, the battery after cycled 30 times is chosen as the test target, and the current
 292 schedules acquired based on the UDDS experiment is repetitively operated until the terminal voltage
 293 reaches the cut-off voltage designated by the manufacturer. Note that when the data length is less
 294 than the pre-set threshold value, the SOC module still uses the previously identified capacity and
 295 parameters to conduct the estimation.

296 Figure 6 shows the current profiles under the UDDS experiment. It can be clearly found that the
 297 entire discharging process takes around 554 minutes. To evaluate the influence incurred by different
 298 data lengths when identifying the model parameters, the data with the duration of 65, 84, 130 and
 299 200 minutes (defined as 65min, 84min, 130min and 200min, respectively) are randomly selected as
 300 the test target, and the remaining data are applied for SOC estimation. Note that when the data length
 301 is 554 minutes (total loading profile process), the SOC is estimated without the update of capacity
 302 value and parameters. Table 3 compares the battery capacity estimation results with respect to
 303 different data lengths. The actual capacity 2.5321 Ah is measured through the calibration test and the
 304 estimated capacity ranges from 2.4366 Ah to 2.5065 Ah. It can be observed that data duration shows
 305 certain influence on estimation results, and the estimated error of battery capacity decreases by
 306 2.7606%, from 3.7716% to 1.011%, after increasing the data length.

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Figure 6. The UDDS current.

309 **Table 3.** The estimation results and errors of the battery capacity corresponding to various data lengths.

Data length	Estimated capacity/Ah	Absolute error/Ah	Relative error/%
65 min	2.4366	0.0955	3.7716
84 min	2.4710	0.0611	2.4130
130 min	2.4854	0.0467	1.8443
200 min	2.5065	0.0256	1.0110

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311 Based on the obtained capacity, the detailed results of SOC and estimation error with different
 312 identification data lengths are presented in Figure 7, and the statistic results are provided in Figure
 313 8. As demonstrated in Figure 7, when the date length increases from 54min to 200min, the estimated
 314 SOC can quickly converge to the reference value according to the updated parameters and capacity,
 315 and the maximum absolute error decreases from 3.643% to 0.989%. When the data length reaches
 316 200min, the estimation errors are restricted within a small range, less than 1%. Besides, Figure 7 also

317 shows the SOC estimation results without considering the capacity's update. The maximum absolute
 318 error, the mean absolute error and RMSE are 2.538%, 1.661% and 1.737%, respectively. It is apparent
 319 that the estimated SOC looks more divergent without the capacity update, thereby manifesting the
 320 advance of the joint estimation algorithm. From Figure 8, we can find that when the data length
 321 increases from 65min to 200min, the maximum absolute error, mean absolute error and RMSE
 322 decrease from 3.643%, 2.331%, 2.498% to 0.989%, 0.234%, 0.319%, respectively. The results
 323 demonstrate that as the calculated data length increases, the estimated SOC becomes closer to the
 324 reference value, this is mainly because the GA shows global optimization ability, and when more
 325 input data samples are referred, the prediction results will be more accurate. Hence, appropriately
 326 increasing the duration of data is beneficial for improving the accuracy of capacity identification and
 327 SOC estimation. Nonetheless, it is appreciably time-consuming when increasing the amount of data
 328 to estimate the battery capacity. To balance the relationship between error and calculation time, the
 329 data duration of 200 minutes is considered as the preferred length. In the following, the estimated
 330 results with the data length of 200 minutes are all adopted for SOC estimation and comparison.

331 **Figure 7.** The results of SOC estimation based on various data lengths: (a) SOC estimation results; (b)
 332 SOC error.

333
 334 **Figure 8.** Comparison of the battery SOC estimation results of different data lengths.

335 4.2 SOC estimation under various degradation stages

336 To verify the feasibility of the proposed co-estimation scheme, the battery cells are
 337 experimentally and circularly tested with the UDDS current at different aging levels. According to
 338 the estimation algorithm of capacity addressed previously, the pre-set data length is 200 minutes.
 339 Table 4 and Figure 9 compare the estimated results of battery capacity at different aging stages (fresh,
 340 nearly fresh, slightly cycled, severely cycled, and lifespan exceeded), of which the number of cycles
 341 ranges from 0 to 120 with 30 as the interval. As illustrated in Table 4, the battery capacity declines
 342 with cycling operation. The proposed algorithm enables that the maximum relative and absolute
 343 errors are less than 1.011% and 0.026 Ah when the battery is cycled for 30 times, thereby indicating
 344 its preferable capability of estimating the battery capacity at different aging status. Furthermore, the
 345 estimated results can also commendably reflect the decay trend of battery capacity.

346

Table 4. The estimated results and errors of the battery during the entire lifespan.

Cycle number	Actual capacity/Ah	Estimated capacity/Ah	Absolute error/Ah	Relative error/%
cyc0	2.5478	2.5344	0.0134	0.5259
cyc30	2.5321	2.5065	0.0256	1.0110
cyc60	2.3788	2.3655	0.0133	0.5591
cyc90	2.1779	2.1758	0.0021	0.0964
cyc120	1.9655	1.9551	0.0104	0.5291

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Figure 9. Capacity value of measurement and estimation at various degradation extents. (a) Estimation results; (b) Relative error.

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After finding the model parameters including the capacity value, the estimated SOC results at different aging status are demonstrated in Figure 10, and the statistic results are summarized in Figure 11. As Figure 10 suggests, it is obvious that when the battery ages, the total discharging time gradually decreases under the same operating condition. The initial SOC is 20% with the error of 80% and the estimated SOC at various aged status can all converge to the reference values. Figure 10 also reveals that the maximum absolute error of SOC is restricted within 1% after the correction of initial SOC error even when the battery is aged, and the convergence time is less than 120 s. As discussed previously, the accuracy of SOC estimation is heavily influenced by the battery degradation. Without considering the update of battery capacity, the SOC estimation error increases towards higher numbers of cycles. In this study, the updated battery capacity is exploited to assist in improving the SOC estimation in the entire lifespan. As can be found in Figure 11, the maximum value of absolute error, mean absolute error and RMSE are 0.987%, 0.484% and 0.566%, occurring in cyc30. The reason is that when the cycle number is 30, the estimation error of capacity reaches 1.011%, thus leading to the worst SOC estimation. Even so, the maximum absolute error of SOC is still restricted within 1.1% after the correction of initial SOC. As the number of battery cycle increases, the estimated SOC error does not increase obviously, manifesting that the updated capacity value contributes to the SOC estimation. From this point of view, regular update of battery capacity in the aging process is imperative to improve the accuracy of SOC estimation.

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Figure 10. The results of SOC estimation with the aged battery cell: (a) SOC estimation results; (b) SOC error.

Figure 11. the estimated errors of the SOC corresponding to aging battery cell.

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372 5. Conclusions

373 In this study, a model-based adaptive joint estimation algorithm of SOC and capacity is
 374 proposed for lithium-ion batteries. The SOC estimation is implemented based on a second-order
 375 ECM with the SRCKF algorithm considering the capacity degradation and parameters variation. The
 376 battery capacity is imported into the model parameter group, and it is jointly identified by the GA
 377 and the constructed TDRS. After obtaining the parameters and capacity, the SOC is accurately
 378 estimated by the SRCKF. Through the experimental validations in terms of different degradation
 379 status, varying duration of recorded data and various dynamic operating conditions, the preferable
 380 performance of the proposed method is satisfactorily verified. The experimental results elucidate that
 381 the co-estimation approach can improve the SOC estimation accuracy in the entire battery lifespan
 382 cycle with the update of capacity, even in the cases of aged batteries and under complicated operating
 383 conditions.

384 In addition, this paper only investigates the SOC and capacity estimation for battery cells.
 385 However, the capacity and SOC of battery packs are also particularly critical in practical applications,
 386 and they will be certainly our research focus in the future.

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 389 J.X., X.S., and J.S.; writing—original draft preparation, Z.C., J.X., X.S. and J.S.; writing—review and
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398 References

- 399 1. Hu, X.; Feng, F.; Liu, K.; Zhang, L.; Xie, J.; Liu, B. State estimation for advanced battery management: Key
 400 challenges and future trends. *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.* 2019, 114, 109334.
- 401 2. Chen, Z.; Shu, X.; Li, X.; Xiao, R.; Shen, J. LiFePO₄ battery charging strategy design considering temperature
 402 rise minimization. *J. Renew. Sustain. Energy* 2017, 9, 064103.
- 403 3. Chen, Z.; Shu, X.; Xiao, R.; Yan, W.; Liu, Y.; Shen, J. Optimal charging strategy design for lithium-ion
 404 batteries considering minimization of temperature rise and energy loss. *Int. J. Energ. Res.* 2019, 43, 4344-
 405 4358.
- 406 4. Zhao, L.; Lin, M.; Chen, Y. Least-squares based coulomb counting method and its application for state-of-
 407 charge (SOC) estimation in electric vehicles. *Int. J. Energ. Res.* 2016, 40, 1389-1399.

- 408 5. Xiong, R.; Yu, Q.; Wang, L.Y.; Lin, C. A novel method to obtain the open circuit voltage for the state of
409 charge of lithium ion batteries in electric vehicles by using H infinity filter. *Appl. Energy* 2017, 207, 346-353.
- 410 6. Houlian, W.; Gongbo, Z. State of charge prediction of supercapacitors via combination of Kalman filtering
411 and backpropagation neural network. *IET Electr. Power App.* 2018, 12, 588-594.
- 412 7. Meng, J.; Luo, G.; Fei, G. Lithium Polymer Battery State-of-Charge Estimation Based on Adaptive Unscented
413 Kalman Filter and Support Vector Machine. *IEEE T. Power Electr.* 2016, 31, 2226-2238.
- 414 8. Li, Y., C. Wang, and J. Gong, A multi-model probability SOC fusion estimation approach using an improved
415 adaptive unscented Kalman filter technique. *Energy*, 2017. 141: p. 1402-1415.
- 416 9. Campestrini, C.; Heil, T.; Kosch, S.; Jossen, A. A comparative study and review of different Kalman filters
417 by applying an enhanced validation method. *J. Energy Storage* 2016, 8, 142-159.
- 418 10. Charkhgard, M.; Zarif, M.H. Design of adaptive H-infinity filter for implementing on state-of-charge
419 estimation based on battery state-of-charge-varying modelling. *IET Power Electron.* 2015, 8, 1825-1833.
- 420 11. Pola, D.A.; Navarrete, H.F.; Orchard, M.E.; Rabie, R.S.; Cerda, M.A.; Olivares, B.E.; Silva, J.F.; Espinoza, P.A.;
421 Perez, A. Particle-Filtering-Based Discharge Time Prognosis for Lithium-Ion Batteries With a Statistical
422 Characterization of Use Profiles. *IEEE T. Reliab.* 2015, 64, 710-720.
- 423 12. Chen, Z.; Fu, Y.; Mi, C.C. State of Charge Estimation of Lithium-Ion Batteries in Electric Drive Vehicles Using
424 Extended Kalman Filtering. *IEEE T. Veh. Technol.* 2013, 62, 1020-1030.
- 425 13. Li, Y.; Wang, C.; Gong, J. A multi-model probability SOC fusion estimation approach using an improved
426 adaptive unscented Kalman filter technique. *Energy* 2017, 141, 1402-1415.
- 427 14. Alkaya, A. Unscented Kalman filter performance for closed-loop nonlinear state estimation: a simulation
428 case study. *Electr. Eng.* 2014, 96, 299-308.
- 429 15. Liu, Z.; Dang, X.; Jing, B.; Ji, J. A novel model-based state of charge estimation for lithium-ion battery using
430 adaptive robust iterative cubature Kalman filter. *Electr. Pow. Syst. Res.* 2019, 177, 105951.
- 431 16. Yu, Q.; Xiong, R.; Lin, C. Online Estimation of State-of-charge Based on the H infinity and Unscented
432 Kalman Filters for Lithium Ion Batteries. *Energy Procedia* 2017, 105, 2791-2796.
- 433 17. Zheng, L.; Zhu, J.; Wang, G.; Lu, D.D.-C.; He, T. Differential voltage analysis based state of charge estimation
434 methods for lithium-ion batteries using extended Kalman filter and particle filter. *Energy* 2018, 158, 1028-
435 1037.
- 436 18. Li, S.; Hu, M.; Li, Y.; Gong, C. Fractional-order modeling and SOC estimation of lithium-ion battery
437 considering capacity loss. *Int. J. Energ. Res.* 2019, 43, 417-429.
- 438 19. Zhang, J.; Lee, J. A review on prognostics and health monitoring of Li-ion battery. *J. Power Sources* 2011,
439 196, 6007-6014.
- 440 20. Waag, W.; Kaebitz, S.; Sauer, D.U. Experimental investigation of the lithium-ion battery impedance
441 characteristic at various conditions and aging states and its influence on the application. *Appl. Energy* 2013,
442 102, 885-897.
- 443 21. Han, X.; Ouyang, M.; Lu, L.; Li, J. A comparative study of commercial lithium ion battery cycle life in electric
444 vehicle: Capacity loss estimation. *J. Power Sources* 2014, 268, 658-669.
- 445 22. Feng, X.; Li, J.; Ouyang, M.; Lu, L.; Li, J.; He, X. Using probability density function to evaluate the state of
446 health of lithium-ion batteries. *J. Power Sources* 2013, 232, 209-218.
- 447 23. Zou, Y.; Hu, X.; Ma, H.; Li, S.E. Combined State of Charge and State of Health estimation over lithium-ion
448 battery cell cycle lifespan for electric vehicles. *J. Power Sources* 2015, 273, 793-803.
- 449 24. He, T.; Xu, W.; Lu, Z.; Yong, H.; Tian, G. Adaptive Fuzzy Logic Energy Management Strategy Based on
450 Reasonable SOC Reference Curve for Online Control of Plug-in Hybrid Electric City Bus. *IEEE T. Intell.*
451 *Transp.* 2018, 19, 1607-1617.
- 452 25. Hussein, A.A. Capacity Fade Estimation in Electric Vehicle Li-Ion Batteries Using Artificial Neural
453 Networks. *IEEE T. Ind. Appl.* 2015, 51, 2321-2330.
- 454 26. Jin, N.; Danilov, D.L.; van den Hof, P.M.J.; Donkers, M.C.F. Parameter estimation of an electrochemistry-
455 based lithium-ion battery model using a two-step procedure and a parameter sensitivity analysis. *Int. J.*
456 *Energ. Res.* 2018, 42, 2417-2430.
- 457 27. Wang, C.; He, H.; Zhang, Y.; Mu, H. A comparative study on the applicability of ultracapacitor models for
458 electric vehicles under different temperatures. *Appl. Energy* 2017, 196, 268-278.
- 459 28. Hu, X.; Li, S.; Peng, H. A comparative study of equivalent circuit models for Li-ion batteries. *J. Power*
460 *Sources* 2012, 198, 359-367.

- 461 29. Liu, L.; Zhang, M.; Buyya, R.; Fan, Q. Deadline-constrained coevolutionary genetic algorithm for scientific
462 workflow scheduling in cloud computing. *Concurr. Comp-Pract. E.* 2017, 29.
- 463 30. Jin, L.W.; Lee, P.S.; Kong, X.X.; Fan, Y.; Chou, S.K. Ultra-thin minichannel LCP for EV battery thermal
464 management. *Appl. Energy* 2014, 113, 1786-1794.
- 465 31. Yang, R.; Xiong, R.; He, H.; Mu, H.; Wang, C. A novel method on estimating the degradation and state of
466 charge of lithium-ion batteries used for electrical vehicles. *Appl. Energy* 2017, 207, 336-345.
- 467 32. Sun, X.; Ji, J.; Ren, B.; Xie, C.; Yan, D. Adaptive Forgetting Factor Recursive Least Square Algorithm for
468 Online Identification of Equivalent Circuit Model Parameters of a Lithium-Ion Battery. *Energies* 2019, 12,
469 2242.
- 470 33. Cheng, S.; Li, L.; Chen, J. Fusion algorithm design based on adaptive SCKF and integral correction for side-
471 slip angle observation. *IEEE T. Ind. Electron.* 2017, 65, 5754-5763.
- 472

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